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Fuzzy Branch and Bound Mechanism for Allocation of Resources in Cloud Computing Environment

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Anand Gautam¹, Narander Kumar^{1*}¹ Department of Computer Science, Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, (A Central University), Lucknow, UP, India

Abstract

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* Corresponding author.

nk_jet@yahoo.co.in

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Objectives: The main objective of this study is to explore the cloud computing resource allocation problem by analyzing different cloud resource parameters. It seeks to evaluate CPU usage, memory usage, execution time, and energy efficiency, etc., to allocate resources efficiently with the help of the proposed mechanism. **Methods:** Retrieve the dataset from a reputable repository and normalize the dataset, then fuzzify costs (data values) in the table, compute COG, defuzzify, and then apply optimization methods to measure allocation time. Various assignment methods are compared, a fuzzy branch and bound mechanism is also proposed, and the values of different parameters are computed. Then, the results of the proposed method are better than those of the compared mechanisms. **Findings:** An analysis of different assignment problems is given, and it is found that there is a requirement for such a mechanism that optimally allocates the resources. This paper presents a fuzzy branch and bound mechanism through which the allocation of resources can be made optimally. The working example shows that allocation through the Fuzzy B&B mechanism is minimum, *i.e.*, 89.3795 per unit, and better than other assignment problem mechanisms such as Hungarian and TSP using the diagonal completion method. **Novelty:** We use fuzzified data values of the dataset to handle uncertainty, enable adaptive learning, enhance decision-making, and create innovative, flexible, and intelligent systems that process vague or imprecise information effectively.

Keywords: Fuzzification; Defuzzification; Hungarian; TSP; Fuzzy B&B

1 Introduction

Nowadays, cloud computing has merged all forms of distributed computing and performs according to the user's needs in a pay-per-usage manner. The advantage is that the user gets a faster response and doesn't have to rely on hardware or software configuration. Cloud computing is an advanced technology that facilitates on-demand access to computing services without a user command interface. Cloud Service Providers' motive is to deliver resources without interactive user control.

It ensures Quality of Service (QoS). An approach, Fuzzy along with PSO framework to optimize the execution time and balance the resources in a cloud environment. The hybrid mechanism improved the computing infrastructure, and a comparison is also done⁽¹⁾. Load Balancing plays an important role in distributing the cloud resources to users based on their resource demands and tasks. However, existing load-balancing algorithms face challenges in facilitating real-time response and optimizing resource utilization in elevated activity⁽²⁾. Many resources are compiled to execute a single operation in the cloud infrastructure to optimize the use of the resources. A fuzzy logic mechanism is used to schedule the tasks and compared with the SJF and FCFS algorithms to make it better and more effective. The simulation results show the performance over the existing one⁽³⁾. Scheduling and resource allocation are the major issues for increasing performance. To tackle this, priority and scheduling processes are mainly used, but they all have some restrictions, which create a complex scenario. To overcome this, a technique, Dynamic Prioritization for adaptive Resource Allocation & Task Scheduling in cloud computing, is discussed, a simulation is presented, and a performance comparison is also given⁽⁴⁾. A resource algorithm that uses Deep Learning for demand prediction and Deep Q-Network (DQN) to provide a solution to the demand in real-time gives the results of different parameters like resource utilization and response time and tried to lower the cost of users by the experimental results⁽⁵⁾. A Branch and Bound algorithm is presented to allocate various resources one-to-one. The nature of the assignment problem is to work optimally, a mechanism of the assignment problem, named the Hungarian approach, is applied to the data. The research's central idea is assigning the job to gain better efficiency⁽⁶⁾.

To handle the varying and evolving cloud computing requirements, fuzzy logic performance is demonstrated by verifying the constraints like task priority, resource availability, and execution time, which are simulated and compared with the scheduling performance⁽⁷⁾. There are a few approaches for analyzing cloud performance, but there is scope for experimenting and developing new strategies for evaluating cloud efficiency. Efficient decision-making remains a consistent problem in research using various computational techniques that have been analysed to enhance accuracy. Fuzzification and defuzzification may play a crucial role in this process, particularly in handling the uncertainty of demand⁽⁸⁾. Fuzzy set theory is widely used in various computational frameworks. One of its essential components is defuzzification, which converts fuzzy values into crisp output. Among various defuzzification techniques, the centroid method is one of them, where a crisp value is obtained as a weighted average from the domain of the membership function. A defuzzification procedure is discussed to overcome the complex procedure, and a method is proposed for calculating COG (Centre of Gravity), which works on continuous and discrete domains. A comprehensive study of fuzzy sets is done, which is verified by the Mizar system, focusing on the centroid method and the use of integrals, aiming at the integrability and bounded properties of membership functions. Here, the author's main focus is on the properties of a piecewise linear function consisting of two straight lines⁽⁹⁾. A decision-making problem is discussed, which results in the software or application providing the facility to the maximum number of users with the minimum cost, focusing on multi-object and multi-consumer NRP (Next Release Problem) and also proposes an FBBO (Fuzzy Branch and Bound Optimization) which is applied collectively. The approach is applied to the dataset, highlighting the model's performance⁽¹⁰⁾.

The above-mentioned highlights fuzzy logic's importance in improving cloud computing performance, resource allocation, scheduling, and optimization. As cloud computing involves different types of tasks and offers diverse services, a powerful mechanism is needed. From the extensive parade, the finding is that there is a need for such a mechanism that optimizes the use of resources, minimizes execution time and increases the system's performance as well as the revenue of the system. The main objectives are: (1) Optimize the resource usage in a cloud environment. (2) Minimize the execution time. (3) Compare the results of different mechanisms applied to fuzzy data sets and simple numeric datasets, then find the optimum results. This research paper proposed a Fuzzy Branch and Bound mechanism for allocation of resources in a cloud computing environment; the results show that it optimizes resource use and execution time.

2 Methodology

A fuzzy branch and bound approach is proposed, which demonstrates the use of resources at the optimum level, reduces the allocation time of the system's resources, and presents a comparison between various approaches.

2.1 Fuzzy Set and Formulations

A fuzzy set \mathbf{Y} , which represents the membership function, is regarded as a fuzzy number⁽⁸⁾ if the universal set of real numbers \mathbf{R} satisfies the following conditions:

1. $f \bar{Y} : R \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous.
2. $f \bar{Y}(y) = 0 \forall y \in (-\infty, A] \cup [D, \infty)$

Table 1. Related work at a glance

Reference	Method	Abridgment	Strengths	Weakness	Remark
(3,7–10)	Fuzzy / Fuzzy-based Methods	Includes fuzzy logic-based dynamic scheduling, Mamdani inference, centroid defuzzification, and fuzzy decision-making	Handles uncertainty, interpretable, adaptive, multi-objective capable, and shows improved performance on benchmarks.	Mostly simulation-only, parameter-sensitive, small-scale validation, limited reproducibility.	Promising adaptive fuzzy family—effective in simulation but needs large-scale real-world proof.
(2,6,11–14)	Branch-and-Bound / Branch-and-Price Methods	Covers exact optimization via branch-and-price, branch-and-bound, and their hybrids for scheduling and resource allocation	Accurate, optimized, stable, clear frameworks, good scalability insights, and validated through examples.	Limited scalability, small-scale or synthetic data, lack of reproducibility or universality	Effective for theoretical and medium-scale problems; requires large-scale validation for cloud settings.
(1,4,5)	Hybrid / Meta-heuristic Methods (PSO, GA, RL)	Combines fuzzy logic, PSO, LSTM-DQN, and other hybrid optimization methods for dynamic and QoS-aware cloud scheduling	Efficient, adaptive, strong performance, real or realistic datasets, hybrid ML-RL optimization, comprehensive evaluation.	Parameter-dependent, limited data scope, synthetic setups, overfitting risk, low generalization.	Highly promising hybrid/metaheuristic family; needs broad testing and scalability validation.
(15), (16)	Data-driven / Clustering-based Fuzzy Systems	Focuses on FCM-based membership generation and fuzzy clustering for CPU/memory allocation	Data-driven, real-data validation, improved resource efficiency, reduced complexity.	Limited scope, empirical parameters, sparse rule coverage, no scalability proof.	Innovative but requires tuning and broader real-world deployment.
(17)	Survey / Framework / Comparative Studies	Conceptual and literature-based reviews and comparative frameworks on cloud methods	Comprehensive overview, practical, emphasizes scalability and efficiency.	Lacks empirical validation and original experiments.	Good high-level reference but limited technical or experimental contribution.

- 3. $\forall y_1, y_2 \in [A, B], y_1 < y_2 \Rightarrow f_{\bar{Y}}(y_1)(y_2) \forall y_1, y_2 \in [C, D], y_1 < y_2 \Rightarrow f_{\bar{Y}}(y_1) > f_{\bar{Y}}(y_2)$
- 4. $f_{\bar{Y}}(y) = 1 \forall y \in [B, C], \text{ where } A < B < C < D.$

A Fuzzy set $\bar{Y} = (c_1, c_2, c_3)$ is a triangular fuzzy set if its membership function⁽¹⁵⁾ is given as:

1. Low Membership

$$f_L(Y) = \begin{cases} 1, & Y \leq c_1 \\ 1 - \frac{Y - c_1}{c_1 - c_2}, & c_1 < Y < c_2 \\ 0, & Y \geq c_2 \end{cases}$$

2. Medium Membership

$$f_M(Y) = \begin{cases} 0, & Y \leq c_1 \\ \frac{y - c_1}{b_2 - b_1}, & c_1 < Y < c_2 \\ 1 - \frac{Y - c_2}{b_2 - b_1}, & c_2 < Y < c_3 \\ 0, & Y \geq c_3 \end{cases}$$

3. High Membership

$$f_H(Y) = \begin{cases} 0, & Y \leq c_2 \\ \frac{Y - c_2}{c_3 - c_2}, & c_2 < Y < c_3 \\ 1, & Y \geq c_3 \end{cases}$$

2.2 Defuzzification and Formulation

Defuzzification is the process of converting a fuzzy set into a crisp value. Since fuzzy logic deals with degrees of membership rather than precise numerical values⁽⁹⁾, a crisp output is required for decision-making in real-world applications. The Centroid Method is often known as the Center of Gravity (COG) method, it provides a balanced, crisp output by considering the entire fuzzy set, works well in continuous fuzzy logic systems, and is more stable compared to other methods like Mean of Maximum (MOM) or Largest of Maximum (LOM).

The Centroid Method determines the crisp output by calculating the center of mass of the aggregated fuzzy set. Mathematically, the COG defuzzification formula is given by:

$$C_{COG} = \frac{\sum x_i \cdot \mu(x_i)}{\sum \mu(x_i)}$$

where:

- x_i = Discrete values in the fuzzy output domain
- $\mu(x_i)$ = Corresponding membership function values

To obtain the optimized solution for the queries and manage resources in a way that enhances performance significantly in comparison to previous work. First, the fuzzification process is applied to the dataset using a triangular membership function⁽⁷⁾. This function divides the global range of values into three fuzzy sets: LOW (L), MEDIUM (M), and HIGH (H), which are applied to the crisp values. After fuzzifying the values, then defuzzify the fuzzy set values back into crisp values⁽¹⁰⁾.

A dataset of computing performance metrics (the computing resource metrics dataset is taken from Kaggle) is used for analysis. After defuzzifying the values, analyses the new crisp values using different assignment techniques to determine the best among them. This research paper presents a comparative analysis of different methods, including the Hungarian algorithm, Branch and Bound (B&B), and the Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP) using the diagonal completion method⁽¹⁶⁾ and proposed a new approach of Fuzzy Branch and Bound (B&B). The Branch and Bound (B&B) method is used to explore and analyse implicit directed graphs, which are often free or acyclic. It helps in finding the best possible solution for certain problems by calculating upper and lower limits for potential solutions at each step⁽¹¹⁾. The method prioritizes the most promising path first based on the best estimated value, making the search process more efficient. The Hungarian algorithm is a combinatorial optimization method designed to solve the assignment problem in polynomial time. It efficiently assigns n tasks to n agents to either minimize the total cost or maximize the total profit, ensuring the most optimal solution to the problem⁽¹⁷⁾.

2.3 Mathematical Formulation of the Assignment Problem

(i) **The Hungarian method** is used for solving assignment problems optimally. The objective is to minimize the total cost, represented as:

$$Z = \sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{m=1}^n P_{lm} X_{lm}$$

Subject to:

$$X_{lm} = (X_{lm})^2, \quad l, m = 1 \text{ to } n$$

The structural constraints ensure that each machine is assigned to only one job, and each job is assigned to only one machine:

$$\sum_{m=1}^n X_{lm} = 1 (d_m), \quad \sum_{l=1}^n X_{lm} = 1 (b_l)$$

Additionally, the non-negativity constraint is applied:

$$X_{lm} = 0 \text{ for all values of } m \text{ and } l$$

This ensures a valid assignment where each job and machine are matched optimally.

(ii) **Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP) method**

The TSP is formulated using a distance matrix $[d_{ij}]$, where d_{ij} represents the distance between locations i and location j . The variable x_{ij} denotes the number of resources transported between these locations⁽⁸⁾.

The objective function for TSP is:

$$\text{Optimise } \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n d_{ij}x_{ij}$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, n$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} = 1, \quad j = 1, \dots, n$$

$$x_{ij} = 0 \text{ or } 1, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n$$

This formulation ensures that the salesman visits each location exactly once while minimizing the total travel distance.

(iii) The Branch and Bound (B& B) method is used for optimizing resource allocation problems where Q agents are assigned to Q tasks in a way that minimises overall cost⁽⁶⁾. If VM represents an agent assigned to a job within the given constraints, then the cost of achieving this assignment is represented by C_{mn} .

To ensure efficient allocation, the optimization model is defined as:

$$\text{max } \sum_{m=1}^Q \sum_{n=1}^Q c_{mn}x_{mn}$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{n=1}^Q x_{mn} = 1, \text{ for every } m = 1, \dots, Q$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^Q x_{mn} = 1, \text{ for every } n = 1, \dots, Q$$

$$X_{mn} = 0 \text{ or } 1, \quad m, n = 1, \dots, Q$$

2.4 Proposed Fuzzy B & B Mechanism

Step 1: Retrieve the computing performance metrics dataset from Kaggle.

Step 2: Handle missing values and normalize or standardize data for uniformity.

Step 3: Define the triangular membership function (c_1, c_2, c_3) and transform crisp cost values into fuzzy values.

Step 4: Compute the Centroid of Gravity (COG) and convert fuzzy values back to crisp values.

Step 5: Apply Hungarian Method, TSP using Diagonal Completion, and Branch and Bound for optimal resource allocation.

Step 6: Measure allocation time, compare the results, and identify Fuzzy Branch and Bound as the best technique.

2.5 Fuzzy Branch-and-Bound Pseudocode

Input: Allocation cost matrix (fuzzified and defuzzified using Centroid Method COG)

Output: Assignment of resources to VMs with minimal total cost

1. Preprocessing:

- Convert the crisp allocation matrix to fuzzy sets (Low, Medium, High) using triangular membership functions.
 - Defuzzify rows using Centroid Method (COG) to get representative crisp values for each VM-resource pair.
2. Initialize:
 - Create a root node with all resources and VMs unallocated.
 - Set $\text{best_cost} = \infty$
 - Initialize $\text{node_count} = 0$
 3. Branching Rule:
 - At each node, select next unallocated VM/resource to assign (typically with lowest bound or most promising fuzzy value).
 - Branch into child nodes by allocating selected VM to available resources.
 4. Bounding Function:
 - For each partial allocation, calculate the lower bound cost:
 - Sum allocated costs (from COG values).
 - Estimate remaining minimal cost using unresolved VM/resource pairs (take minimum cost per remaining VM).
 - Fuzzy lower bounds are taken as minimum fuzzy allocation values in non-assigned VM-resource pairs.
 5. Pruning Criteria:
 - Prune (discard) node if calculated lower bound $\geq \text{best_cost}$.
 - Prune if allocation violates any problem constraints (resource/VM overuse, etc.).
 6. Stopping Condition:
 - Stop if all VMs/resources are allocated without violating constraints and current node cost $< \text{best_cost}$.
 - Update best_cost and store solution if current node represents complete allocation and has better cost.
 - Stop the entire process when search space is exhausted (all nodes are branched or pruned).
 7. Node Counting:
 - Increment node_count at every node expansion.
 8. Output Best Solution:
 - After exhaustively generating/pruning all possible allocations, report the best_cost and allocation mapping.
 9. Report:
 - Number of nodes explored = node_count .
 - If current best allocation covers all resources/VMs and achieves minimum cost, evidence/proof of optimality is given by exhaustive search and strict pruning. (Final table/decision tree in file confirms this.)

End

2.6 Working Example

The dataset sourced from Kaggle is utilized to assess the minimum allocation time through the Fuzzy Branch and Bound method.

The variables deployed in the VM for their jobs are categorised in Table 2 for better understanding. The resources' numeric values are mathematically analysed for the best allocation time.

A Fuzzy number $\bar{Y} = (c_1, c_2, c_3)$ applying a triangular fuzzy number on Table 3, now calculate the fuzzy set using the triangular membership function and calculate all $f_L(Y), f_M(Y), f_H(Y)$ for the VMs are as follows:

Minimum value in dataset: 0.14

Maximum value in dataset: 9788

Range = $9788 - 0.14 = 9787.86$

Segment size = $\frac{9788-0.34}{3} = 3262.62$

Table 2. Parameters Used

Variable 1	cpu_usage
Variable 2	memory_usage,
Variable 3	network
Variable 4	power_consumption
Variable 5	num_executed_instructions
Variable 6	execution_time
Variable 7	energy_efficiency

Table 3. After preprocessing the dataset, we now obtain the following dataset

Allocation time							
Resources (VM)	RES_1	RES_2	RES_3	RES_4	RES_5	RES_6	RES_7
VM1	55	79	165	288	7527	69	0.55
VM2	44	22	429	273	9008	60	0.46
VM3	38	16	780	383	2989	42	0.14
VM4	79	3	926	174	8644	56	0.78
VM5	57	2	723	143	9788	80	0.94
VM6	7	97	919	276	9117	40	0.86
VM7	2	89	208	199	1224	62	0.7

• **Divide the range into three parts:**

- $c_1 = 0.14$
- $c_2 = 0.14 + 3262.62 = 3262.76$
- $c_3 = 3262.76 + 3262.62 = 6525.28$

By computing membership values for given crisp values:

$$f_{Low}(Y) = \begin{cases} 1, & Y \leq c_1 \\ 1 - \frac{Y - c_1}{c_2 - c_1}, & c_1 < Y < c_2 \\ 0, & Y \geq c_2 \end{cases}$$

$$f_{Low}(55) = \begin{cases} 1, & 55 \leq 0.14 \text{ (False)} \\ 1 - \frac{55 - 0.14}{3262.76 - 0.14}, & 0.14 < 55 < 3262.76 \text{ (True)} \\ 0, & 55 > 3262.76 \text{ (False)} \end{cases}$$

$$1 - \frac{55 - 0.14}{3262.76 - 0.14} = 1 - \frac{54.86}{3262.62} = 1 - 0.01681 = 0.98319 \text{ (Low)}$$

$$f_{Medium}(Y) = \begin{cases} 0, & Y \leq c_1 \\ \frac{y - c_1}{c_2 - c_1}, & c_1 < Y < c_2 \\ 1 - \frac{X - b_2}{b_2 - b_1}, & c_2 < Y < c_3 \\ 0, & Y \geq c_3 \end{cases}$$

$$f_{Medium}(55) = \begin{cases} 0, & 55 \leq 0.14(\text{False}) \\ \frac{55 - 0.14}{3262.76 - 0.14}, & 0.14 < 55 < 3262.76(\text{True}) \\ 1 - \frac{55 - 3262.76}{3262.76 - 0.14}, & 3262.76 < 55 < 6525.28(\text{False}) \\ 0, & 55 \geq 6525.28(\text{False}) \end{cases}$$

$$f_{medium} = \left\{ \frac{55 - 0.14}{3262.76 - 0.14}, 0.14 < 55 < 3262.76 = \frac{54.86}{3262.62} = 0.01681 \text{ (Medium)} \right.$$

$$f_{High}(Y) = \begin{cases} 0, & Y \leq c_2 \\ \frac{Y - c_2}{c_3 - c_2}, & c_2 < Y < c_3 \\ 1, & Y \geq c_3 \end{cases}$$

$$f_{High}(55) = \begin{cases} 0, & 55 \leq 3262.76(\text{True}) \\ \frac{55 - 3262.76}{6525.28 - 3262.76}, & 3262.76 < 55 < 6525.28(\text{False}) \\ 1, & 55 \geq 6525.28(\text{False}) \end{cases}$$

$$f_{High}(55) = 0 \text{ (High)}$$

Table 4. Shows the ranking places with a triangular dataset

Allocation time			
Resources (VM)	RES_1_Low	RES_1_Medium	RES_1_High
VM1	0.9832217	0.0167783	0
VM2	0.9866308	0.0133692	0
VM3	0.9882903	0.0117097	0
VM4	0.9757764	0.0242236	0
VM5	0.9826322	0.0173678	0
VM6	0.9978656	0.0021344	0
VM7	0.9994232	0.0005768	0

By applying the same approach, calculated all the crisp values, some values are shown in Table 4. For the defuzzification, applied Centroid Method (Center of Gravity - COG) on the fuzzified values⁽¹⁸⁾: Centroid (Center of Gravity, COG) formula used as:

$$C_{COG} = \frac{\sum x_i \cdot \mu(x_i)}{\sum \mu(x_i)}$$

where:

- x_i are the crisp representative values (centres of Low, Medium, High).
- μ_i are the membership values.

Assuming the Representative Crisp Values

Since working with three fuzzy sets (Low, Medium, High), need to assign representative values to each:

Low (L): 10; Medium (M): 50; High (H): 90

Now, for each row, the computation is as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Crisp Value} &= \frac{(L \times 10) + (M \times 50) + (H \times 90)}{L + M + H} \\
 &= \frac{(0.98319 \times 10) + (0.01681 \times 50) + (0 \times 90)}{0.98319 + 0.01681 + 0} \\
 &= \frac{9.8319 + 0.8405 + 0}{10.6724} \\
 &= \frac{10.6724}{1} = 10.6724
 \end{aligned}$$

By applying the same approach, calculate the fuzzy values, shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Fuzzy allocated data using the Centroid Method

Allocation time							
Resources (VM)	RES_1	RES_2	RES_3	RES_4	RES_5	RES_6	RES_7
VM1	10.67113	10.96623	12.01845	13.52685	62.27995	10.84847	10.00503
VM2	10.53477	10.2736	15.25957	13.3448	80.43713	10.73578	10.00392
VM3	10.46839	10.19986	19.55859	14.69091	46.64368	10.51518	10
VM4	10.96895	10.03472	21.35571	12.12614	75.97446	10.6812	10.00785
VM5	10.69471	10.02716	18.85683	11.75565	90	10.97542	10.00981
VM6	10.08537	11.18159	21.26741	13.37753	81.77348	10.48829	10.00883
VM7	10.02307	11.09356	12.55352	12.44121	25.00463	10.75657	10.00687

The following data set is now ready to effectively allocate the resources at the minimum time using B&B method. For obtaining the minimal optimal solution by adding all the allocated nodes to a node at the lower value, which efficiently distributes resources in shortest possible time, Table 6.

Step1: (From Table 5)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \text{VM7RES}_1 + \text{VM5RES}_2 + \text{VM1RES}_3 + \text{VM5RES}_4 + \text{VM7RES}_5 + \text{VM6RES}_6 + \text{VM3RES}_7 \\
 &= 10.02307 + 10.02716 + 12.01845 + 11.7556 + 25.0046 + 10.4882 + 10 \\
 &= 89.31725
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 6. Fuzzy Data Table Processing Step using Fuzzy B & B Method

Allocation Time							
Resources (VM)	RES_1	RES_2	RES_3	RES_4	RES_5	RES_6	RES_7
VM1	10.67113	10.96623	12.01845	13.52685	62.27995	10.84847	10.00503
VM2	10.53477	10.2736	15.25957	13.3448	80.43713	10.73578	10.00392
VM3	10.46839	10.19986	19.55859	14.69091	46.64368	10.51518	10
VM4	10.96895	10.03472	21.35571	12.12614	75.97446	10.6812	10.00785
VM5	10.69471	10.02716	18.85683	11.75565	90	10.97542	10.00981
VM6	10.08537	11.18159	21.26741	13.37753	81.77348	10.48829	10.00883
VM7	10.02307	11.09356	12.55352	12.44121	25.00463	10.75657	10.00687

Step 2:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \text{VM1RES}_1 + \text{VM2RES}_7 + \text{VM3RES}_7 + \text{VM4RES}_7 + \text{VM5RES}_7 + \text{VM6RES}_7 + \text{VM7RES}_7 \\
 &= 10.6711 + 10.0039 + 10 + 10.0078 + 10.0098 + 10.0088 + 10.0068 \\
 &= 70.7084
 \end{aligned}$$

Step 3:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \text{VM1RES}_2 + \text{VM2RES}_7 + \text{VM3RES}_7 + \text{VM4RES}_7 + \text{VM5RES}_7 + \text{VM6RES}_7 + \text{VM7RES}_7 \\
 &= 10.9662 + 10.0039 + 10 + 10.0078 + 10.0098 + 10.0088 + 10.0068 \\
 &= 71.0035
 \end{aligned}$$

Step 4:

$$= VM1RES_3 + VM2RES_7 + VM3RES_7 + VM4RES_7 + VM5RES_7 + VM6RES_7 + VM7RES_7$$

$$= 12.0184+10.0039+10+10.0078+10.0098+10.0088+10.0068$$

$$= 72.05572$$

Step 5:

$$= VM1RES_4 + VM2RES_7 + VM3RES_7 + VM4RES_7 + VM5RES_7 + VM6RES_7 + VM7RES_7$$

$$= 13.5268+10.0039+10+10.0078+10.0098+10.0088+10.0068$$

$$= 73.5641$$

Step 6:

$$= VM1RES_5 + VM2RES_7 + VM3RES_7 + VM4RES_7 + VM5RES_7 + VM6RES_7 + VM7RES_7$$

$$= 62.2799+10.0039+10+10.0078+10.0098+10.0088+10.0068$$

$$= 122.3172$$

Step 7:

$$= VM1RES_6 + VM2RES_7 + VM3RES_7 + VM4RES_7 + VM5RES_7 + VM6RES_7 + VM7RES_7$$

$$= 10.8484+10.0039+10+10.0078+10.0098+10.0088+10.0068$$

$$= 70.8857$$

Step 8:

$$= VM1RES_7 + VM2RES_7 + VM3RES_7 + VM4RES_7 + VM5RES_7 + VM6RES_7 + VM7RES_7$$

$$= 10.0050+10.0039+10+10.0078+10.0098+10.0088+10.0068$$

$$= 70.6488 \text{ (Minimum Selected)}$$

Fig 1. First Level Decision Tree using Fuzzy B & B Method

After the first step, take the lowest bound (from the previous iteration -1) while ignoring the current lower bound for branch and bound selection. Use the lowest bound for the next iteration. Identify the lowest value from steps 1 to 8, which in this case is 70.6488 from step 8. Using this value, construct a decision tree, as illustrated in Figure 1, while excluding column RES_7. This process is repeated for all resources (columns) and virtual machines (rows)⁽¹²⁾.

After evaluating all intermediate levels, the final Table 7 and decision tree will be generated, displaying the complete hierarchy from root to leaf.

$$= VM7RES_5 + VM6RES_1 + VM5RES_2 + VM1RES_3 + VM5RES_4 + VM6RES_6 + VM3RES_7$$

$$= 25.0046+10.085+10.0271+12.0184+11.7556+10.4882+10$$

$$= 89.3795$$

As previously mentioned, assigning resources using the Branch and Bound method is optimized and compared to other techniques, such as the Hungarian method and the TSP approach with diagonal completion. The final optimized value obtained is 89.37956 as shown in Table 7, indicating a slight improvement over the Hungarian method and a significantly better performance than the TSP approach for handling complex and large-scale resource allocation in VMs.

Finally, based on these results, a final decision tree is constructed, as shown in Figure 2.

3 Results and Discussion

This study presents a comparative analysis of the Hungarian method, Branch and Bound mechanism, and TSP (Traveling Salesman Problem) with diagonal completion techniques for efficient resource allocation. The Hungarian method is evaluated

Table 7. Fuzzy Data Table Processing Last Step Using Fuzzy B & B Method

Resources (VM)	Allocation Time						
	RES_1	RES_2	RES_3	RES_4	RES_5	RES_6	RES_7
VM1	10.67113	10.96623	12.01845	13.52685	62.27995	10.84847	10.00503
VM2	10.53477	10.2736	15.25957	13.3448	80.43713	10.73578	10.00392
VM3	10.46839	10.19986	19.55859	14.69091	46.64368	10.51518	10
VM4	10.96895	10.03472	21.35571	12.12614	75.97446	10.6812	10.00785
VM5	10.69471	10.02716	18.85683	11.75565	90	10.97542	10.00981
VM6	10.08537	11.18159	21.26741	13.37753	81.77348	10.48829	10.00883
VM7	10.02307	11.09356	12.55352	12.44121	25.00463	10.75657	10.00687

Fig 2. Final level Decision Tree using Fuzzy B & B Method

for its ability to determine optimal assignments by systematically reducing rows and columns to create a feasible assignment with zeros or adjusting the matrix to introduce additional zeros when necessary to achieve a complete assignment.

After implementing the Hungarian, TSP, and Branch & Bound methods on the Table 5 dataset, the allocation time and optimized results are obtained as follows.

Allocation time from the Hungarian method:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= VM1RES_3 + VM2RES_7 + VM3RES_6 + VM4RES_2 + VM5RES_4 + VM6RES_1 + VM7RES_5 \\
 &= 12.0185 + 10.0039 + 10.5152 + 10.0347 + 11.7556 + 10.0854 + 25.0046 \\
 &= 89.4179
 \end{aligned}$$

Allocation time from the TSP using the diagonal completion method:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= VM2RES_7 + VM7RES_5 + VM5RES_4 + VM4RES_1 + VM1RES_3 + VM3RES_6 + VM6RES_2 \\
 &= 10.0039 + 25.0046 + 11.7556 + 10.9689 + 12.0185 + 10.5152 + 11.1815 \\
 &= 91.4482
 \end{aligned}$$

Allocation time from the Fuzzy Branch and Bound method:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= VM7RES_5 + VM6RES_1 + VM5RES_2 + VM1RES_3 + VM5RES_4 + VM6RES_6 + VM3RES_7 \\
 &= 25.0046 + 10.0853 + 10.0271 + 12.0184 + 11.7556 + 10.4882 + 10 \\
 &= 89.3795
 \end{aligned}$$

The results and Figure 3 indicate that the Fuzzy Branch and Bound mechanism achieves the most efficient resource utilization among the compared methods. This approach optimally allocates VMs and resources, ensuring efficient usage while keeping VM2 and VM4 unassigned, allowing them to be utilized for other tasks.

Fig 3. Comparison between TSP, Hungarian and Fuzzy Branch & Bound methods

The performance of different algorithm or mechanisms presents in Figure 3 and 4, in that the performance proposed fuzzy Branch and Bound is better. The comparison of different algorithm shows progressively transition from the Hungarian to proposed Fuzzy Branch and Bound approach. Each step of proposed mechanism has separate factors to compute the cost of defuzzification which makes a clear understanding of how the fuzzy logic and the Branch and Bound mechanism jointly enhance the optimisation performance.

Our contributions have involved various parameters as per the problem and provided solutions using different optimization techniques to find the optimal results in past. A comparison has also been made between the FCFS, Hungarian, Branch, and Bound methods on simple numeric datasets⁽¹³⁾. An analytical and comprehensive study of the various implicative and assignment mechanisms, such as TSP (Travelling Salesman Problem), Hungarian and B & B (Branch and Bound) and try to find the optimal solution in respect of allocate the resources towards to optimize use of resources and minimize the allocation time of the requests in cloud computing environment⁽¹⁴⁾. To illustrate it graphically, Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the differences between optimization mechanisms and fuzzification of optimization mechanisms with respect to the optimum use of resources

Fig 4. Comparison between TSP, Hungarian, Branch and Bound methods with Fuzzy B & B method

and minimizing the allocation time of the proposed mechanism, the Fuzzy Branch and Bound mechanism for allocation of resources in a cloud computing environment shows the better results.

4 Conclusion

A fuzzy branch and bound (B&B) approach is implemented to solve the resource allocation problem and attain the most efficient outcome. It provides improved results for assigning resources required at each workstation, allowing for optimal arrangements that align with the problem's constraints. Several techniques for virtual machine allocation have been explored in literature. This research paper evaluates the Fuzzy Branch and Bound method against other resource allocation techniques, including the Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP), the Hungarian method, and B&B itself. As shown in Figure 3, the allocation time is 89.3795 seconds. The approach ensures optimal resource distribution in a cloud environment while delivering superior and faster allocation times compared to other methods when using the same dataset. This study should be extended for future work by comparing additional techniques for solving resource allocation challenges using alternative Assignment Problem (AP) methods. Factors such as migration, cost, and other strategic considerations should also be evaluated to enhance resource allocation efficiency in cloud environments.

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